

Co-funded by
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Human Brain Project

EBRAINS CoCreate: Improved Investigation of Brain-related Disorders

February – March 2023

*Research and innovation roadmaps with long-term ambitions
and visions.*

Facilitated by EBRAINS Community Building Team

EBRAINS
Community

Introducing EBRAINS

EBRAINS is a new digital research infrastructure, created by the EU-funded Human Brain Project, that gathers an extensive range of data and tools for brain related research. EBRAINS will capitalize on the work performed by the Human Brain Project teams in digital neuroscience, brain medicine and brain-inspired technology, and will take it to the next level.

The EBRAINS ambition

EBRAINS draws on cutting-edge neuroscience, big data, computing, robotics and related technologies to help translate the latest scientific discoveries into innovation in medicine and industry, for the benefit of patients and society. EBRAINS' ambition is to provide the scientific community at large with an open state-of-the-art capability that fosters collaborative brain science, opens the way to ground-breaking discovery and aims to secure Europe's leading position in the dynamically growing field of multidisciplinary brain research and its exploitation.

EBRAINS

Introduction

The **EBRAINS Community** is being built with and for the people developing, using, supporting, and benefiting from the EBRAINS Research Infrastructure, with an interdisciplinary and inclusive focus. In this context, the **EBRAINS CoCreate** process is a strategic community engagement process, which facilitates multi-actor collaboration on research and innovation roadmaps.

Research and innovation (R&I) agendas are generated at many different scales and levels, and by many different bodies, including the European Commission, governments, research agencies, funders, institutions, and individual researchers. A known tendency in this setup is that the scope is often limited by institutional thinking, disciplinary boundaries, or special interests. This leaves a need for defining research agendas across fields and actors, thereby defining more comprehensive and less biased priorities or directions for R&I programmes or projects.

EBRAINS CoCreate builds on the method of Open Research Agenda Setting (ORAS) which recognises the benefits of engaging multi-actors including civil society organisations, patient organisations and governance bodies in R&I development alongside scientific and technological experts. The resulting research agendas will in turn include visions or problems that societal actors find important, which strengthens and legitimises the selection of research priorities.

The **EBRAINS CoCreate Improved Investigation of Brain-related Disorders** process is made up of five workshops arranged from February 2023 to March 2023 with the following set-up:

The **EBRAINS CoCreate Improved Investigation of Brain-related Disorders** aims to:

- 1) Identify shared long-term ambitions within the areas of disorder identification and treatment.
- 2) Create roadmaps that allow the ambitions to evolve into tangible goals, tracks, and steps.
- 3) Identify opportunities to realise the R&I roadmaps.

How vision-based research and innovation can solve complex problems

Open Research Agenda Setting has previously been used in projects such as [CIVISTI](#) and [CIMULACT](#). The method is based on establishing collaborations between researchers and the society impacted by their research. The purpose is to cocreate projects that are built on clearly formulated visions, based on a need in society.

Contrary to a dream, which can be anything imaginable, a vision is founded in knowledge and it is realizable. It can be broken down to tangible goals and missions.

When working with visions, the first step is to specify the general characterisation of the vision. In later steps, the vision is broken down into R&I activities and roadmaps. The key is to divide the vision into something that can be done. When it is presented as a set of into manageable actions, it is easier to lobby for, to find collaborators, and to ensure funding – and in the end to materialise the vision.

Try to imagine your research as if you were an explorer with a vision of sailing among the icebergs. You might decide to go to Greenland, and then, instead of just trusting your luck, you do some planning to find the best way to get there. You might plan to go west, as you have heard about a great place for hunting deer and whales.

Then you make a map – a detailed roadmap that describes where you want to go and why you would like to go there.

Then you start planning in more detail. What do you need to succeed? You'll find your crew and

team members, so you'll have all the right skills on board. And then you finally begin the journey. First you travel to Shetland and then to the Faroe Islands, where you know you can get fresh water and other supplies. From there you travel to Iceland and then to Greenland.

That's basically the same thing we do in Open Research Agenda Setting:

- We bring society and researchers together, to brainstorm and find a clear vision.
- We then cluster the vision and make it more solid.
- And then we break it down and create the roadmap.

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CoCreating a Roadmap on Improved Investigation of Brain- related Disorders – an EBRAINS initiative

This CoCreate on “Improved Investigation of Brain-related Disorders”, takes up the challenge of envisioning a future in which *individual* brain disorders are investigated using a comprehensive understanding of brain, body, and environmental health, and lifespan perspective. The discussions and roadmaps this CoCreate facilitated focus on expanding and improving the investigation of brain related disorders.

The vision of EBRAINS CoCreate Improved Investigation of Brain-related Disorders is a future where individualized precision processes are the norm in healthcare. Each person's unique multidimensional physical and mental health, clinical history, and environmental factors are thoroughly analysed and compared with data from thousands of other individuals using advanced technologies like pattern recognition and normative modelling. This allows for tailored and precise treatments that are personalized to each person's specific needs and circumstances, leading to better health outcomes and a higher quality of life.

Can we imagine an individualized precision process in which individual (longitudinal) multidimensional physical and mental health, clinical and environmental information is compared with information of thousands of other individuals by means of e.g., pattern recognition and normative modeling? If we can – how may this lead to new insights for identifying available best intervention and treatment practices? How can new insights inform basic, translational, and clinical research efforts, and the development of new, more personalized, preventive, and clinical treatment strategies, and (public) health policies?

To achieve this vision, EBRAINS CoCreate sketches an ambitious and promising roadmap and defines which first steps can be realised by collaboration across disciplines and stakeholders. To this end, a multidisciplinary group of participants, consisting of experts and stakeholders in the fields of neuroscience, neurology, psychology, psychiatry, ethics, health data security, AI, and big data analysis, was gathered. The participants collectively had insights into the relevant challenges and possibilities, as well as potential solutions and their realization.

A Roadmap to achieve Improved Investigation of Brain-related Disorders - Envisioning a new patient assessment system

Developing a patient assessment system for brain disorders faces challenges such as creating a user-friendly interface, proactive assessments, and continuous improvement. Proposed solutions include establishing standardized processes, metadata systems, ethical consent processes, adaptive models, and educational resources through collaborative efforts with private foundations and the European Commission. The vision for continuous improvement involves version control, and agile methodologies. The ultimate goal is to improve patient outcomes and advance research in the field of brain disorders.

A roadmap is a strategic plan that defines a goal or desired outcome and the major steps or milestones needed to reach it. The development of roadmaps in EBRAINS CoCreate Improved Investigation of Brain-related Disorders made use of a wide range of deliberative formats including horizon scanning, open brainstorming, ideation, co-creation and online collaborative spaces.

The discussions and the roadmap presented in this CoCreate report focus on expanding and improving the investigation of brain related disorders by developing a new patient assessment system. It highlights the need for collaboration among a wide range of stakeholders and the utilization of human, data and equipment resources, including funds, a knowledge-sharing platform, and an organization to ensure effective workflows.

Two concrete issues, which are prerequisites for establishing a new patient assessment system are a) the build up of human capacity through interdisciplinary research, extending academic infrastructure, and interdisciplinary collaboration, and b) investments in the development of new research methodologies together with industry partners, like wearable devices that could collect contextual and individual biomarkers. This highlights the need to overcome the lack of clear phenotypes within brain-related disorders and to develop new methods for measuring brain function.

To assist in making informed decisions about diagnosis or treatment, the use of new models is proposed, which could be machine learning models based on normative data or databases that find the most likely diagnosis or cases most similar to the patient and return the most probable effective treatment. Such models would aim to improve the precision of diagnosis and treatment prediction. An added proposition is to have models informed by neuroscience that can be used to address specific issues, where, for example, no conventional diagnosis guidelines exist or where there are "white spots" in diagnostic manuals. The combination of brain models and machine learning could facilitate personalized investigations as well as improved classification of brain diseases, and a sense of how such a new patient assessment system works may be facilitated by a description of the experience of the system for four persons – two of them being 'in front' of the system, and two of them working in the 'backend' of the system.

Max (patient) has issues he is not able to control. He has received a visitation for a psychiatric investigation, and now Max is sitting in front of Dr. Louise in the local hospital. They have a longer talk which circulates around the life story of Max and his own understanding of his behaviour and the issues he has, and Louise has taken notes all along. Louise then asks him if he has read the consent form sent to him beforehand, and if he wants to sign it, thereby allowing the department to analyse his situation using the available public data about him. Max signs, and Louise runs a first screening of Max in the system, asks Max some additional questions and adds the information in the system. Louise asks Max to sign in for a blood test to analyse his situation more precisely. She arranges a new consultation and provides him with access to an online questionnaire that he should answer before they meet next. Max feels optimistic. Louise is really listening to him, and her questions are obviously relevant and push him to talk about those parts of his life and situation that he worries about. It is nice that she doesn't try to jump to conclusion - she seems to do what she can to get the information she needs before concluding anything. On the one hand it would be nice if there was an easy answer, but on the other, when there isn't it is nice that she explores the situation deeper.

Louise (clinician): The new investigation system certainly has received strong attention from Louise. She has taken several courses in the use of the system, and she is also leading a small user-community across the hospitals in the region. Now she has Max in her consultation and after having reported the main observations from their initial dialogue into the system and having received his consent she runs a first scan of Max. The system compares available data on the life history, health records, etc. on Max with all available patients across Europe. In the first scan it finds 15.689 patients that have a history that may be comparable to that of Max, so the system asks Louise to input further data that Max should be able to answer. Now the system accordingly reduces the number of comparable patients to 5.329. The system asks Louise to provide genetic data of Max, and it provides a link to a survey for Max to answer. A first indication of the range of sub-diagnoses that may be relevant for Max is presented, but with the disclaimer that the result has a large variability across the compared patients, so no conclusions should be drawn yet. Louise informs Max that a profile

of his issues is beginning to take form; however, it is too early to conclude anything, so she makes an agreement with Max about the next steps. Louise is optimistic about the next consultation; she feels certain that it will narrow down the results to about 20-30 (anonymous) patients with cases resembling Max's, thereby informing her of the interventions which were most effective for those patients. Hopefully the system provides concrete diagnosis, which would provide her with intervention guidelines. But she knows that this is not always the case – sometimes the diagnosis doesn't point to a clearly defined condition, in which case the system provides information about other patients with a comparable profile. In any case, this is not a decision-making system, it is a support system, and it is her experience that discussions in the usual clinical meetings about a patient have improved in quality since they began to use the system - they are now able to pinpoint the interventions much more precisely already by the first analysis. And, not the least, the effectiveness of the investigations has improved. Louise and her colleagues save precious time, partly because self-reporting from the patients is very effective, and partly because the precision of the system saves the clinicians and the patients for long periods of trial-and-error treatments.

Kate (project manager in a national system hub) is having a meeting at her workplace CPP – Centre for Personalised Psychiatry, which is the national hub for the new European investigation system for brain-related disorders. The national centre is responsible for quality assurance of the specialised sub-models of five disorders, including Alzheimer disease. They are arranging a workshop next week in the CPP Working Group on Alzheimer's Analysis. The workshop is to revisit the data pool behind the Alzheimer's sub-model, which is mainly put to use by the main models in the system when the scan of a patient indicates early Alzheimer's symptoms and deeper, specialised analysis is needed. The working group has asked for this workshop to be arranged because new research has indicated that the sleep patterns of a patient can be analysed at an early stage based on social media data about the patient. Kate and her colleagues are putting together a program for the workshop, which involves researchers across the globe and a review from a group of researchers. Kate expects that this will result in an update of the sub-model data access, so the workshop will include data ethics experts and NGO's. Kate is not worried about the success of the workshop – it is now a standard procedure for hubs all over Europe to set up such quality assurance workshops, and the results show increasingly higher satisfaction with the system among clinicians.

Thierry (responsible for system educations at European central system hub): Leading an international group of clinicians, scientists and administrators is a challenge. Thierry's day started with a long online meeting with discussions about how to update international education guidelines on data acquisition and data quality. The existing education guidelines were evaluated half a year ago, and one of the conclusions was that there was too much variation across nations regarding the effectiveness of data acquisition and the quality of data curation, and this could be explained by the lack of streamlined education targets. Thierry was then given the responsibility to lead a cross-national group tasked with developing updated and uniform training schemes for data providers, managers, and curating teams. It was a difficult meeting, but they have finally passed a milestone since as they agreed upon the main content of the education modules – something Thierry and his teams had worked on for four months. The next phase will be to detail the module curricula for the different target groups. Challenging, but important.

This storytelling about a day in the life of four persons hopefully gives an idea about the patient assessment process and investigation system that the CoCreate vision may result in. It is a system that compares the patient with other patients across Europe, and provides a match, which may result in a precise formal diagnosis, but always results in a pool of other cases from which experiences of treatments can be drawn. It would not only result in a system – it would be an international organisation that constantly improves the system, the data behind it, educations, ethics standards, and which develops as knowledge and data develops, and would require scientific development and innovation in neuroscience, including the use of genomics, neuroimaging, and other technologies to identify biomarkers that can guide differential diagnosis and recommend therapy tailored to the patient. The importance of multimodal data integration and the development of new, reliable tools to identify personal health-to-disease trajectories is emphasized. To make progress in this field, there is a need to collectively develop a common understanding of the challenges and their associated solutions.

Roadmap illustration

First and foremost, realising a new patient assessment system requires the collaboration of various stakeholders and the utilization of necessary resources. Challenges include creating a user-friendly interface, dividing tasks between humans and machines, early detection and intervention, proactive assessments, and continuous improvement.

As displayed in the following roadmap illustration the roadmap includes three consecutive projects indicating the maturity level towards full integration of the proposed new patient assessment system:

- A **Ramp-up project phase** to establish standardised assessment processes, metadata annotation systems, ethical informed consent processes,
- a **Proof-of-concept project phase** to establish, adaptive models, and educational resources, and
- an **Implementation project phase** that involves a core team to establish a knowledge-sharing platform, and an organisation to ensure effective workflows.

Moreover, the roadmap illustrates the five sub-topics divided into colours. Each coloured circle or square illustrates an action point described in the belonging sub-topic.

- A **circular action point** indicates that the action is a system action. These actions are crucial for the development and proper functioning of the system and refers to tasks or initiatives that need to be undertaken to enhance or optimise the system. They may involve developing new features, improving existing processes, or implementing changes to ensure the system operates efficiently.
- A **square action point** indicates that the action is an institutionalising action. These actions are crucial steps towards implementing and integrating the new patient assessment process into the system. They focus on establishing policies, procedures, and resources that promote the adoption and sustainability of the proposed system.

The following pages show the overall roadmap towards a new patient assessment system, and in the following chapters, six overarching theme are described, which were developed during the workshop series in the spring of 2023. Each of the themes has an introduction to the actions needed to contribute to the overall vision of developing a new patient assessment process. The introduction is followed by a set of actions representing the major steps or milestones needed. Each action includes a challenge- and solutions overview, as well as a description of the required collaborators and resources.

List of themes

1. Legal and ethical compliance
2. Data acquisition
3. FAIR Data
4. Models needed for the patient assessment
5. Innovation and science needs

Recap of the roadmap

To make models adaptive to individual patient settings, version control and change management processes must be implemented. Regular assessments of the patient assessment process can identify areas for improvement, and agile methodologies can facilitate continuous feedback and updates throughout the development process. Ultimately, this initiative could improve patient outcomes and advance research in the field of brain disorders.

Overall Challenges: Creating a user-friendly interface, dividing tasks between humans and machines, early detection and intervention, proactive assessments, and continuous improvement pose significant challenges in developing a patient assessment system for brain disorders.

Overall Solution: To tackle these challenges, we propose an architecture project costing 5M€ over three years and a prototyping project costing 30M€ over five years. These projects will establish a metadata annotation system, adaptive models, standardized assessment processes, ethical consent processes, and educational resources for stakeholders.

Overall Collaboration: Collaborators could include private foundations, the European Commission's Directorate-General for Research and possibly the Directorate-General for Health, and joint projects among member states. We could seek political and professional ambassadors and engage professionals, authorities, and politicians in conferences and other events to ensure ownership of the vision and roadmap.

Overall Resources: We will require funds, a core team to manage the project, a knowledge-sharing platform for clinicians, an economic analysis of costs, and an organization to ensure effective workflow.

Overall Characterisation: To make the models adaptive to individual patient settings, we will implement version control and change management processes to track and document updates to the knowledge base. Clinicians and patients will provide feedback on the knowledge base, which will be continuously updated through machine learning algorithms. User-friendly interfaces will be developed for clinicians to input and customize automated processes.

Overall, Vision for Continuous Improvement: Agile methodologies will facilitate continuous feedback and updates throughout the development process. A roadmap with milestones and performance indicators will be developed to measure progress and adjust the vision as necessary. Regular assessments of the patient assessment process will identify areas for improvement and adjust the vision accordingly. Crowdsourcing end-user feedback loops and conducting regular meetings and workshops for stakeholders will facilitate continuous improvement.

In conclusion, developing a patient assessment system for brain-related disorders is a challenging task that requires collaboration among many disciplines and stakeholders, and the utilization of a wide variety of resources. The use of models based on machine learning and formalised neuroscientific knowledge can assist in making informed decisions about diagnosis or treatment, and the development of new research methodologies and the integration of multimodal data can help advance the field of personalized medicine.

1. Legal, ethical, and societal compliance

This theme aims to develop data sharing policies that balance researchers' and clinicians' need to use human data with the rights of data subjects. Challenges include clarifying legal and ethical responsibilities, addressing risks posed by personalized medicine and AI, and mitigating potential negative consequences for individuals. Achieving this requires systematic inquiry, stakeholder engagement, and routine validation. Actions to achieve this include public support, good research practices, a unified data policy, stress testing data-sharing platforms, expert guidance, and continual improvement through public engagement.

Introduction

The aim of this sub-topic is to develop data sharing policies which empower researchers and clinicians to utilise human data, whilst protecting the rights of the data subjects in question.

This addresses the potential challenges that arise before research, whilst using the data, and in view of further handling of it.

Firstly, it will pave the way to clarify legal accountability and ethical responsibility of research conduct. Concerning the second point, two potential challenges are Personalised Medicine as well as Artificial Intelligence, insofar as the former comes with additional risk of unintended and inaccurate associations made about data subjects, while the latter requires an interdisciplinary and continuous discussion given the rapid advances. Lastly, this sub-topic aims to address the possible consequences for individuals of their variables being known and used.

Achieving this goal entails grappling with complex ethical, legal, and societal challenges, which will require systematic academic inquiry, multi-stakeholder engagement and routine review and validation to overcome.

We suggest that the following actions are required to achieve this:

- Any developments must be justified and receive public support - this should be based upon a

programme of research concerning public perceptions of personal data sharing.

- Universities, hospitals, and research organisations should define good research practice and research integrity and should empower and protect researchers to conduct high quality research.
- Develop a multi-national unified data policy which can facilitate data sharing across boundaries.
- Implement a research programme to investigate the potential opportunities which personalised medicine provides for patients, to opt in and out of the usage of certain data points, and the ethical implications of this type of autonomy.
- Systematically stress-test platforms designed for sharing sensitive data to ensure that the data is adequately protected, this can be achieved through red team hacking techniques.
- Institutions should provide expert support, advice, and guidance to researchers to properly consider the potential implications of their research.
- Institutions should advise researchers, clinicians, and IT departments to make data available for federated privacy preserving analysis as an alternative to acquiring patient consent.
- Finally, these systems should be continually improved and iterated upon based upon further engagement with the general public.

Actions overview of the sub-topic

Institutionalising Action: Study public perceptions of data governance (transformation)

Challenge overview: We do not know what people think is acceptable handling of their data.

Solution overview: Any large-scale research project needs public support and needs to make a positive contribution to the public good. Funders should put calls out to gather perceptions of how publics think their data should be handled, and based upon that research a subsequent suite of pilot studies can be made to develop the rest of the programme.

Collaborators needed: Funding bodies, researchers, data subjects (perhaps through advocates).

Characterisation of the action: A systematic programme of research inquiry into public perceptions of data governance.

Resources: Funding for a number of calls to study these subjects. 15-20, 2-3m Euro projects across Europe.

Institutionalising Action: Legal protection for data subjects

Challenge overview: [LEGAL] Legal protections for research participants who are sharing data (privacy policy).

Solution overview:

- “red team”: ethical hackers who try to exploit data protection vulnerabilities; as technologies for data protection improves, stay up-to-date & fix new problems that arise.
- Identify national differences in implications of known biomarkers, anonymization of vulnerable data, how to deal with asymmetric bilateral information flow.
- Develop tools for online/cloud-based analysis and workflow in order to reduce data security risk/leaks stemming from local downloading.

Collaborators needed: Research institutions, funding bodies, researchers, data subject representatives (patient representatives), technologists/developers.

Characterisation of the action:

Resources: N/A

System Action: Unified data sharing policy

Challenge overview:

- [LEGAL] Making sharing of health data across borders possible in a timely fashion (within localities, within the EU and internationally): differences in laws.
- Which geography and how to expand?
- → *Can a globally accepted set of ethical principles even exist?*

Solution overview:

- Stakeholder Mapping Exercise: all data protection authorities, govts, clinicians, data subject representatives across jurisdictions.
- Make a case for the importance of working on this.
- Data protection policy “strength” mapping across jurisdictions.
- Creating a central organization to overlook and unify different member organizations (i.e., universities) facilitating data sharing across members. Should be initiated and tested at a more local level (i.e., national) as a proof of concept before more global dissemination.

Collaborators needed:

- Public representatives (patients, data subjects in general).
- Experts: clinicians, researchers, data protection officers, lawyers, ethicists etc.
- Politicians and policy makers.

Characterisation of the action: Long-term, multi-stakeholder project (akin to the development of GDPR).

Resources: Money, time, research data (derived from the study of public perceptions).

Institutionalising Action: Legal protection for researchers

Challenge overview: [LEGAL] Legal protections for researchers who are sharing data.

Solution overview: Support of the university legal team for researchers at all times - all steps of the data collecting and sharing process should be supported by lawyers and research leadership (with involvement of actual researchers and technicians who are “on the ground”).

Collaborators needed: University/hospital legal and research offices, lawyers, researchers.

Characterisation of the action: Developing training schemes for those experts/lawyers.

Resources: Resources to hire experts/lawyers in those departments, and effectively train them.

Institutionalising Action: Understanding dual use

Challenge overview: Responsibility: Dual Use - military, commercial, insurance etc. How responsible are researchers for how their data is used legitimately by other parties? How to bring together interests of funding industry and research responsibility?

Solution overview: Studies/systems/products (perhaps scaling by size/investment/scale) should invest in foresight/horizon scanning to consider the implications of their work. Part of funding applications, journal paper editing processes.

Collaborators needed: University research offices, researchers.

Characterisation of the action: Initiative to improve research support offices. Establishment of a training scheme for research support office staff to allow them to support researchers.

Resources: Funding to employ such individuals in research offices, and to train them. The funding required would differ from institution to institution.

Institutionalising Action: Justice system interplay

Challenge overview: Criminal liability based on research/disease finding.

Solution overview: N/A

Collaborators needed: Government, legislature judging on possible implications: experts.

Characterisation of the action: Project (extension of (and somewhat an example for) unified data policy).

Resources: N/A

Institutionalising Action: Control AI in research

Challenge overview:

- How to accommodate and account for explainability, reliability, and bias in AI data (especially due to restrictions of IP).
- Can you use output for final decision making/consequences to people/institutions/laws?
- (<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence-altai-self-assessment>)

Solution overview: Demand legally that researchers: control the update of software (how often is it updated? do not use old data).

Collaborators needed:

Characterisation of the action: Ongoing development.

Resources:

Institutionalising Action: Taking responsibility for AI

Challenge overview: Legal responsibility.

Solution overview: Demand legal responsibility for the released AI.

Collaborators needed:

Characterisation of the action: Ongoing discussion about recent AI developments.

Resources:

2. Data acquisition

This theme addresses challenges associated with data acquisition for investigating brain-related disorders. The challenges include providing continuing education for researchers, determining the types of data needed, and collecting a large normative dataset for effective comparisons. To overcome these challenges, it is suggested to collect multiple variables such as physiological and psychological markers using updated datasets, develop multiscale signatures of healthy brains, and use models such as Bayesian Networks for diagnostics and risk assessments. The ultimate goal is to improve clinical decision-making for personalized treatment and prevention.

Introduction

The task of our group was to focus on identifying challenges and solutions associated with data acquisition in the investigation of brain-related disorders.

We identified two main forms of challenge: i) those associated with the researchers themselves, and ii) those associated with the data acquisition by those researchers. With respect to the researchers themselves, we believe that it will be critical to provide continuing education possibilities for researchers as new techniques, analysis pathways and scientific results are determined. With respect to data acquisition, critical issues related to the determination of sample representation, sample size, and data type (data modality).

As these become resolved, core data acquisition products - denoted biomarkers, the identification of at-risk individuals and treatment indications will be determined. The acquisition of a large normative dataset will enable the data of a single individual to effectively be compared with data from large numbers of prior individuals, so that patterns and insights determined from these prior dataset can inform the clinical decision-making regarding the single individual.

To resolve the challenge of determining what types of data that are needed, multiple variables need to be collected and tested. Potential variables could be the measured (objective) physiological markers and reported (subjective) psychological traits on brain activity (healthy brain vs diseases) under different conditions. We propose to detect/identify markers using the up-to-date datasets and initiate the implementation of new standards with respect to novel software and devices.

The models demand investigation of the relationship between the measured physiological responses (e.g., advanced wearable devices in field studies). Development of multiscale signatures of healthy (vs sick) brains based on whole-brain computer simulations by obtaining more reliable measurements/registration (plus the development of new evaluation forms) with better temporal resolution/ for time-based integration. Models (such as Bayesian Network) should be considered the core for diagnostics or interrelationships/impacts of various features, assessing the risks/probabilities of disease development under different conditions (such as high levels of emotional, cognitive and/or mental overload).

Actions overview of the sub-topic

Institutionalising Action: Education on data collection

Challenge overview: Allow researchers and health professionals to add to the investigation and identify needs.

Solution overview: Educate personnel, who are relevant to the field, to improve the quality of the data. E.g., Construct MRI sequences optimal to detect the relevant signal.

Collaborators needed:

- Universities and hospitals.
- EBRAINS.

Characterisation of the action: Development of an educational framework and program tailored to the target group.

Resources: The education should be integrated in the educational programs for health care professionals and researchers. EBRAINS should provide a platform for virtual training courses and more specific courses for specific target groups.

System Action: Securing representative sample acquisition

Challenge overview: How to secure a representative sample (population level, specific clinical populations)?

Solution overview:

- Investigate the demographic data on participants.
- Oversample, if necessary, groups identified underrepresented in clinical samples.

Collaborators needed: An organization (e.g., Statistics Denmark or the US Census this will be country specific, Eurostat), responsible for generating a description of the demographics of the population that can be used as the basis for test sample development.

Characterisation of the action: Collaborative project.

Resources: Funding for the process (should be relatively minor).

System Action: Test of sample size and power

Challenge overview: How much data is needed, and what sample sizes are required?

Solution overview:

- Use simulated data to test the power.
- Machine learning is a tool that could aid in sample size calculation.

Collaborators needed: Statisticians.

Characterisation of the action: Harmonization of sample size decisions.

Resources: EBRAINS should develop an independent platform to calculate power based on existing data.

System Action: Biomarker identification and modeling

Challenge overview: Identify biomarkers and integrate into a computational model of disease.

Solution overview:

- 1st identify **plausible** neuroimaging and other clinical markers of risk profile pertinent to the disease in question (possibly, before and after intervention).
- Then, build a model using the **plausible** biomarkers. Apply the model on an independent sample to test reproducibility and eventually develop normative/reference (e.g., height and weight growth models for healthy growth in children, healthy aging) models.

Collaborators needed: Universities, hospitals and social institutions, Neuroscience R&D Centers, start-ups.

Characterisation of the action: Collaborative projects.

Resources: Financial resources for relevant research projects.

System Action: Defining need and choice of data type

Challenge overview: Deciding how to choose which types of data are needed?

Solution overview:

- Inclusion of multiple variables to characterize a disease (to differentiate diseases with overlapping symptoms)
- mindful of sample size.
- Narrow down data types according to empirical utility (data types that don't replicate become extinct).

Collaborators needed: Universities, hospitals and social institutions.

Characterisation of the action: Collaborative projects.

Resources: Financial resources for relevant research projects.

System Action: Identifying at-risk individuals

Challenge overview: Identification of vulnerable individuals.

Solution overview:

An iterative process:

- Use of registry data to identify first markers, even if imprecise, of vulnerability.
- Use validated biomarkers to identify individuals at risk.
- Future work can then target individuals with these markers to develop more precise (bio)markers.

Collaborators needed: Hospitals, universities and municipalities, schools, workplaces.

Characterisation of the action: Collaborative projects.

Resources: Financial resources for relevant research projects.

System Action: Identification of new treatment paradigm.

Challenge overview: Treatment (implications) development

Solution overview: Based on the identified population-at-risk and the biomarker identification and modeling→ utilize as tool for testing treatment/interventions.

Collaborators needed:

- Universities, hospitals and e.g., pharmaceutical industry.
- Neuroscience, R&D Centers.

Characterisation of the action: Projects/research programs.

Resources: Investigator initiated studies (in collaboration with the pharmaceutical industry).

3. FAIR data

Efficient sharing of medical data is hindered by its heterogeneity across hospitals and research projects. The proposed solution involves establishing acquisition and organization standards, transforming data into universal formats, and developing machine learning approaches. FAIR data principles are implicit in this approach, which also involves federated analysis to overcome privacy concerns. An education system for stakeholders as well as connection between federations are also recommended. Finally, the need for continuous updating of standards to accommodate technological developments is suggested.

Introduction

The heterogeneity of medical assessment across hospitals and research projects hampers their value. One of the first objectives to share efficiently the acquired data is to propose data acquisition and organization standards for each modality of interest (imaging, genetics, other omics, clinical assessments, etc.). This involves both adapting the parameters of each acquisition system to align the output with a template and transforming the data into universal formats integrating all the metadata necessary for research and medical decision-making. At a meta level, we will have to propose for each pathology a set of priority modalities in a research context, and an optimal simplified protocol in a clinical context. A continuous effort to update the standards will be necessary to take account of technological developments and discoveries. It will be important to set up an education system to make all stakeholders aware of the importance of these standards and data sharing. A complete ecosystem will have to be put in place to support the community (access to the detailed description of the standards, format transformation tools, MOOCs, etc.). In order to be able to retrospectively exploit datasets from

incompatible standards, machine learning approaches will be developed to harmonize them at the level of raw data or extracted features. In parallel, new machine learning methods robust to data heterogeneity will be designed for the prediction and stratification of patient groups.

Privacy considerations for medical sensitive data often prohibits the analysis in a centralised way, as data cannot be shared outside hospitals. To federate data access and analysis, all previously mentioned steps have to apply, i.e., the datasets are homogenised and an optimal metadata schema is adopted. However, a more widespread application of federated analysis in a real - world setting with datasets that reside in hospitals would help to move forward existing solutions regarding federated data management, federated learning (ml/ai), and privacy techniques such as anonymisation and pseudonymisation, encryption, differential privacy, secure multi - party computation etc. Finally, a connection between federations would also be possible via appropriate interfaces.

Actions overview of the sub-topic

Institutionalising Action: Educational program to advertise FAIR data principles

Challenge overview: Acceptability / Consensus of Common Metadata Model.

Solution overview:

- Educational program to advertise FAIR data principles and given options for each SILO.
- Pushing labs to include FAIR principle in their local culture.

Collaborators needed: Data managers research PIs EBRAINS.

Characterisation of the action: Turning FAIR principles as a “must do”.

Resources: Communication and education human resources.

Institutionalising Action: Developing a curation ecosystem (tools & community) via FAIR Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs)

Challenge overview:

- Addressing retrospective/prospective curation.
- Lack of incentive for FAIR.
- Silos in research labs - difficulty to adopt new data models.

Solution overview:

- User-friendly web based EBRAINS curation ecosystem.
- High quality FAIR MOOC CI/CD with integrated EBRAINS Curation Collaboratory and FAIR community interaction.

Collaborators needed: Data managers research PIs EBRAINS.

Characterisation of the action: Creation of a complete ecosystem from EBRAINS to support data curation.

Resources: Project for extending EBRAINS curation process.

System Action: Promote federated learning adaptation and data model standardisation

Challenge overview: Complexity of a federated setting (remote nodes). Encourage adoption of federated learning solutions and standardise data models for federation.

Solution overview: International coordination, more installations across Europe to create, test, evolve federated learning solutions.

Collaborators needed: Hospitals (Legal department, IT department Clinicians, Researchers), Associations (disease specific), Technical solution providers, Computer Science / ML / AI engineers.

Characterisation of the action: Long-term development.

Resources: IT resources (Cloud, on premise), technical staff, research staff, financial resources.

System Action: Standardise data acquisition for research

Challenge overview: Heterogeneity of sensors and datasets.

Solution overview:

- Adoption of common standards (for each sensor modality, tuning of the parameters is required to align the data across sensor models toward such a standard).
- At a metalevel, create (ontology) based guidelines to sensor selection (pathology-wise).

Collaborators needed:

- Sensor manufacturers, -service platform supporting multicenter data collection.
- Research on sensor design.
- Multicenter data collection projects.

Characterisation of the action: A large effort is required in each domain at the onset of the process, a permanent follow-up to integrate technological evolutions.

Resources: Physicists, travelling subjects testing different sensors, data repository.

System Action: Standardise data acquisition for clinics

Challenge overview: Heterogeneity of sensors and datasets.

Solution overview: Propose guidelines for clinics, pathology by pathology, for simplified standard acquisitions compatible with the normative values issues from research.

Collaborators needed:

- Sensor manufacturers, -service platform supporting multicenter data collection.
- Research on sensor design.
- Multicenter data collection projects.

Characterisation of the action: Prioritize the most important modalities from research results, in order to provide a reasonable guideline for clinics.

Resources:

System Action: Standardise interface between federations

Challenge overview: Reusability of datasets after the initial agreement / clinical trial the patients gave consent form.

Solution overview: Work with legislation/ethical boards to give permission to research participants to agree to share their information according to FAIR data principle.

Collaborators needed: Computer science, legal / ethics boards.

Characterisation of the action: Long-term development.

Resources: Software/ML engineers.

System Action: Extended testing of current approaches to real world federations

Challenge overview: Privacy challenges in federated learning - adding noise while not compromising data utility, anonymisation, encryption.

Solution overview: Application of privacy preserving tools in a variety of settings / datasets, automation of tools.

Collaborators needed: Computer Science / ML / AI engineers, Clinicians, Medical researchers.

Characterisation of the action: Long-term development.

Resources: Machine learning engineers, Data Scientists, Computing infrastructure resources.

System Action: Designing robust machine learning algorithms to deal with heterogeneity

Challenge overview: Heterogeneity of sensors and datasets.

Solution overview:

- Machine learning algorithms that deal with heterogeneous data. This is a new field of research letting ML algorithm find structures in the data.

or

- Statistics or ML algorithms performing a posteriori harmonization of cross-sensor data before the final analysis.

Collaborators needed: ML research field.

Characterisation of the action: These two solutions correspond to developing fields of research, that will set up some general strategies from the first use cases.

Resources: Software / ML engineers and researchers, Computing resources (Cloud, on premise)

Datasets to be harmonized with a benchmark.

Guideline: Design versatile strategies

Challenge overview: Dealing with sensor and neuroscience models evolutions.

Solution overview: Expandable and generalizable models?

Collaborators needed: All.

Characterisation of the action: This is a general statement, not really an action, just a guideline.

Resources: Software / ML engineers and researchers, Computing resources (Cloud, on premise).

4. Models needed for the patient assessment

Developing models based on machine learning and neuroscience can improve the precision of diagnosis and treatment prediction. Steps to achieving this include harmonizing datasets, gathering multiscale data, establishing a funding scheme, securing infrastructure, developing models, assessing their quality, and implementing them in the healthcare system. Quality assurance of predictive models is essential, and guidelines are needed for reliability. The focus should be on involving interdisciplinary collaborations and stakeholders to achieve these goals, including the implementation of models in the healthcare system with ethical and practical evaluations.

Introduction

Imagine how to use “models” in assisting making informed decisions about diagnosis or treatment. One method could be a ML model that based on normative data or databases would find the most likely diagnosis. or find the cases most similar to the examined patient and return with the most probable effective treatment.

In this subtopic actions to take for developing models needed to aid in the diagnosis of patients is outlined, and several steps to the roadmap are proposed, including harmonizing datasets, gathering multiscale data, establishing a funding scheme, securing infrastructure, developing models, assessing their quality, and implementing them in the healthcare system.

The models would be based on machine learning and neuroscience, and they would aim to improve the precision of diagnosis and treatment prediction. There should be a focus on quality assurance of predictive models to ensure their reliability. The proposed actions to the roadmap suggests involving various stakeholders and interdisciplinary collaborations to achieve this goal.

Another view is to have specific models informed by neuroscience (neural models, neural systems, neural mass models) that can be used to address very specific issues, where for example no conventional diagnosis guidelines exist or where there are “holes” in the diagnostic manuals. This could for example models of how medicine will respond, given x , y , z , parameters related to the patients that will help for example optimize dose or treatment type. The combination of brain models and machine learning could facilitate classification of brain diseases ([Triebkorn et al. 2022](#)). There will need to be a focus on robust quality assurance of predictive models for diagnosis—especially when/if the models are being used to assist decision making processes. There need to be a set of guidelines on the minimal performance required for being considered reliable. Possible parameters could be accuracy, consistency, agreement between independent models/run of the same model, among other possible factors. EBRAINS should be a leading voice in this discussion and facilitate democratic involvement of relevant stakeholders.

In the following, we outline what are the initial steps and building blocks we think are needed:

1. Harmonize datasets to make sure the models are based on “good”/representative data. To harmonize the datasets, it will be good with community consensus guidelines to facilitate better integration. Make a “Good practice”/recommendations for collecting data for large databases (similar to other community methods guidelines “good practice papers). This could be achieved by including researchers (and other stakeholders) as a consensus group to formulate the outline. Timewise this can already be initiated. The guidelines should address the following issues:
 - Handle data limitations/getting unbiased data: account for biases in the data, update questions/measures investigated to obtain a full multimodal picture.
 - Achieve patient stratification to account for heterogeneity: aggregate clinical research studies, a posteriori data harmonization)
 - Include contextual/societal factors into the data gathered, focus on interdisciplinarity.
 - Address what data exists and what data is missing. Lead to a call for action.
 - Reach and consult the investigated public: improve outreach to the underrepresented populations and involve members of the communities of interest to consult the creation of diagnostic tools and formulation of questionnaires by harnessing the power of the community members’ knowledge from lived experience (outsider would not think of certain factors to be included in the research, or could use phrasing that would be misunderstood)
2. Gathering multiscale data: assessing status quo of data, existing data and data gaps - what models and combinations of models are possible? This would be done by individual research groups, who contribute to large shared European cohorts in the spirit of UK biobank.
3. Funding scheme: a founding scheme should be proposed including suggestions on resource allocation, e.g., which fields of interest should be prioritized, which models should be favoured for

development/updating/validation. This could be achieved by engaging stakeholders (decide priorities by consensus), performing risk assessment (decide priorities by urgency/severity), and involving expert consultation (eminent doctors/researchers decide priorities). Moreover, longitudinal, and large projects carried out by interdisciplinary collaborations should be incentivised, facilitated, and funded by announcing large collaborative grants.

4. It is necessary to secure the infrastructure, ie. software and hardware for working with the models by investing in software development (grants) and providing computational power for modelling by EBRAINS (FENIX & HPC).
5. Model development & integration has to include sequential steps, first designing clustering algorithms for simple similarity-based diagnosis, then integrating knowledge-based models e.g., representing mechanisms of diseases, neuromodulation, medication, inferring biomarkers. Integrated models (meta-models) and connecting models at different scales (micro-macro) and/or levels (cells, receptors, connectome)

could help increase precision of diagnosis and/or treatment prediction/planning.

6. Model assessment is necessary for assuring high precision and quality of diagnosis/prediction. This could be done by EBRAINS using their collection of models & datasets. Performance should be tested across all rank performance and stratified applicability. Organizations/systematic research projects should be established to update and validate models.
7. Implementation of models in the health care system, including ethical & practical evaluation and considering the responsibility & limitations of the physician.

References:

Triebkorn P, Stefanovski L, Dhindsa K, Diaz-Cortes MA, Bey P, Bülow K, Pai R, Spiegler A, Solodkin A, Jirsa V, McIntosh AR, Ritter P; Alzheimer's Disease Neuroimaging Initiative. Brain simulation augments machine-learning-based classification of dementia. *Alzheimers Dement (N Y)*. 2022 May 15;8(1):e12303. doi: 10.1002/trc2.12303. PMID: 35601598; PMCID: PMC9107774.

Actions overview of the sub-topic

System Action: Good practice for collecting data for large databases/modeling guidelines

Challenge overview:

- Handling data limitations (biased/incomplete/outdated data fueling models).
- Achieve patient stratification to account for heterogeneity.
- Include contextual/societal factors in modeling.
- Reaching and consulting the investigated public.

Solution overview:

Make a “Good practice for collecting data for large databases” - guidelines for researchers on how to get it representative across the database (e.g., call for data on underrepresented groups, diseases, methods, species, data types, etc.).

- Update questions categorizations asked in studies to reflect new information/findings;
 - Account for biases in the model, state the limits of your research.
 - Aggregate clinical research studies to reach dataset sizes large enough to tackle stratification (which means that a posteriori data harmonization can be performed).
 - Gather information on far more contextual/societal factors than currently.
- Focus on interdisciplinarity.
 - Improving outreach to the underrepresented populations and involving members of the community of interest. Consulting with relevant populations: creating diagnostic tools and formulating questionnaires appropriately measuring what we want them to measure.
- Harnessing the power of community members’ knowledge from lived experience (outsider would not think of certain factors to be included in the research, or could use phrasing that would be misunderstood).

Collaborators needed:

- Who/stakeholders: researchers working with aggregating data and meta-science.
- Representatives from the public?
- Someone (EBRAINS?INCF?) guiding the process?

Characterisation of the action:

Time plan: Is anything in the way for doing this now?

- Guidelines to drive community focus/funders.
- Suggest guidelines for research funders over following years.
- Update “call for data” over the entire period.

Resources:

- People resources

Institutionalising Action: Funding scheme

Challenge overview:

- Resource prioritization: How do you prioritize which diseases warrant the focus of resources? For model development/updating/validation.
- Facilitate longitudinal studies.
- Facilitate large projects by interdisciplinary large.

Solution overview:

- Stakeholder engagement (decide priorities by consensus)?
 - Risk assessment (decide priorities by urgency/severity)?
 - Expert consultation (eminent doctors/researchers decide priorities).
- Plan longitudinal studies.
- More incentive for collaborative projects.

Collaborators needed: Funders (as “a call for action” to funders and stakeholders).

Characterisation of the action:

Resources: Necessary financial support.

System Action: Secure infrastructure

Challenge overview:

- Software/hardware for models.
- Lack of computational power to train the models.

Solution overview:

- Invest in software development (grants?).
- Gain computational power for modelling: EBRAINS (FENIX & HPC).

Collaborators needed: EBRAINS members.

Characterisation of the action: Ongoing.

Resources: Resources for infrastructure.

System Action: Gathering multiscale data

Challenge overview:

- Detect which data is missing, which models are available.
- Gather data for multiscale disease signatures is expensive and difficult.

Solution overview: Organize large shared European cohorts in the spirit of UKbiobank

Collaborators needed: EBRAINS Knowledge Graph Team, Digital Brain Atlasing Team.

Characterisation of the action: Ongoing.

Resources: Individual input.

System Action: Data harmonisation

Challenge overview: Using/pooling EBRAINS datasets.

Solution overview: Data harmonization: find which variables are comparable across which datasets, OR how can you bring variables from different studies/datasets into the same “space” / normalize them?

Collaborators needed: INCF, EBRAINS Curation Team.

Characterisation of the action: ASAP?

Resources:

System Action: Model development & integration

Challenge overview:

- Different applications:
 - Clustering (diagnosis).
 - Tracking and predicting disease trajectories (etiology).
 - Neuromodulation effects (treatment prediction/planning).
- Connecting models at different scale (micro-macro) and level (cells, receptors, connectome).

Solution overview: Organize large shared European longitudinal cohorts in the spirit of UKbiobank.

Collaborators needed: E.g., TVB, NEST Community.

Characterisation of the action: Ongoing.

Resources: Individual input

System Action: Model assessment

Challenge overview:

- Dealing with a zoo of models without necessary consensus.
- Who is responsible for updating models?
- Are models better than AI-like systems which match patient data to similar/alike data in a system (a la EBRAINS vision)?

Solution overview:

- EBRAINS models & datasets. Test performance across all; rank performance/stratify applicability?
- Establish organizations/systematic research projects to update and validate models to keep them current.
- Organize systematic competitions between model-based and AI-based strategies.

Collaborators needed: Clinical trials like EPINOV.

Characterisation of the action:

Resources: Individual input.

Institutionalising Action: Implementation in healthcare

Challenge overview:

How to get the “models” from researchers to clinics.

- As basic knowledge.
- As classification of patients.

As specific models of sub-systems, effects, etc. (e.g., model of how a drug would affect a brain network to predict treatment effect).

Solution overview:

- What are the needs? Perhaps there is not an explicit need, but as models become better and available, they will find a use?
- Models/algorithms, if used for direct clinical decision, would need a CE mark or equivalent?

Collaborators needed: Possibly up to the individual research groups/developers, and industry?

Characterisation of the action:

Resources: Clinical guidelines for use of “models”.

5. Innovation and science needs

Advances in genomics, neuroimaging, and other technologies have enabled the development of personalized approaches to brain-related disorders. However, the lack of non-invasive biomarkers and the complexity of these disorders have hindered progress in clinical practice. To overcome these challenges, interdisciplinary research and development of new methodologies are necessary. Additionally, a multimodal approach combining neuroimaging and other biomarkers using AI solutions could identify individuals at risk for these disorders, leading to personalized treatments and prevention.

Introduction

There is a growing effort to develop a more personalized and precise approach to brain-related disorders, employing genomics, neuroimaging, and other technologies to identify biomarkers that can guide differential diagnosis and tailor patient-centered therapy. However, these advances have not been implemented in clinical practice at the desired pace, and it is clear that, regardless of technological progress, the importance of multimodal data integration is needed as well as the development of new reliable tools to identify personal health-to-disease trajectories.

One reason for this is the lack of non-invasive biomarkers, which makes it difficult to diagnose these disorders accurately and monitor their progression. Another challenge is the complexity and heterogeneity of these disorders, which makes it challenging to identify effective treatments.

However, to make progress in this field, we need to work together to develop a common understanding of the challenges and their associated solutions. By sharing our insights and experiences, we are proposing two pathways: the actions toward building human capacity and actions toward personalize medicine.

Actions forward building human capacity

To achieve outcomes it is necessary to build human capacity. Model building based on interdisciplinary research (from psychiatry to endocrinology, physiology, genetics, sociology, environmental, communication) is required to understand the causes, identify manifestations, and identify biomarkers. For example, develop more holistic training and development of incoming researchers. This can be achieved by formalizing multidisciplinary supervision of Master and PhDs so that the students are exposed to multiple approaches to a given research topic. Even in the undergraduate years it would be necessary to introduce students to this approach to any research. Specifically, this can be encouraged by having educational programs that require multiple supervisors from different disciplines.

This approach requires extending academic infrastructure. This will include interdisciplinary collaboration (such as data contribution, and research trajectory), and would require including this approach in educational programs related to research. For AI multimodal integration, it is essential to ensure the existence of appropriate scientific infrastructures that will allow rapid transmission of notable scientific findings, such as infrastructures which are highly interdisciplinary.

Actions toward personalized medicine

The first challenge we identified was to get less proximal measures of brain function, getting more reliable measures (or forms of assessment), getting measures with better temporal resolution and temporal-based integration. Thus, we will need investment in the development of new research methodologies, like wearable devices with more sensitive sensors that could collect contextual and individual biomarkers data (voice, face microexpression, body fluids etc). We identify that the innovation and technology development should be done together with the industry partners.

The second challenge was how to overcome the lack of clear phenotypes within brain-related disorders, especially regarding the concept of looking for the brain as a separate system from the whole body and the concepts of "peripheral" versus "central". The solution we proposed was to implement a multimodal approach regarding combinations of neuroimaging and other OMICS biomarkers (transcriptomics, epigenetics, genetics, proteomics, metabolomics, lipidomics and exposomics) using AI solutions to identify individuals at risk for the development of brain-related disorders. Implementing such an approach would lead us to new tools and solutions to generate new/modified phenotypes and health trajectories to be used in personalized treatment but also prevention. Investments in research with this focus should be prioritized by funding agencies and ERC.

Actions overview of the sup-topic

System Action: Develop research which can make use of EBRAIN - Measure development

Continue to Reflect on a pre disease focus for research and broaden the discussion with other interested groups. Identify funding resources and apply for funding. Conduct a comprehensive literature review legacy research which may have already taken this approach. Plan: identify existing research methods appropriate to this agenda and develop new research methods to further improve the method. Action: Develop research which can make use of EBRAIN and the Human Brain Project which lends itself to the approach, as well as other sources. Evaluate the findings and disseminate.

Challenge overview:

- Getting less proximal measures of brain function.
- Getting more reliable measures (or forms of assessment).
- Getting measures with the better temporal resolution.
- Temporal-based integration.

Solution overview: Investment in the development of new research methodologies, like wearable devices with more sensitive sensors that could collect contextual and individual biomarkers data (voice, face micro expression, body fluids etc.).

Collaborators needed: Develop contacts related to the EBRAINS broker role to enable other potential collaborators to connect with other collaborators. Develop contacts with organisations developing devices for biomarkers for brain diseases or changes which indicate disease elsewhere etc. Develop contacts with pharmaceutical companies and neuroscientists involved in the development of biomarkers, in particular in the EU].

Characterisation of the action: Identify relevant contacts in the European Medicines Agency e.g. to liaise on EU Medical Device regulation^[1] for advice on wearable devices which can be disseminated through EBRAINS to other potential collaborators.

^[1] <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/human-regulatory/overview/medical-devices>

Resources: Personnel: Key stakeholders who influence the type of research which is undertaken. Develop an interest group to communicate this to the broader community through for example, conferences, papers and other valued communication resources. Lobby groups responsible for funding to support a shift in focus so that funding is provided or research on pre-disease changes in the brain and the broader researcher agenda of non-invasive bio markers. Lobby lifestyle advocates to take a broader approach to preventative treatments and the use of wearables.

E.g., EU council of Ministers. Health Policy: European Health Committee (CDSP). Develop ongoing relationship with – e.g. Scientific Committee on Health, Environmental and Emerging Risks (SCHEER)^[1] Monitor the Website of the Council Working Group on Open Science^[1] for relevant workshops and advocate for the setup of a working group for e.g. pre disease changes in the brain and research.

^[1] <https://erc.europa.eu/about-erc/thematic-working-groups/working-group-open-access>

^[1] https://health.ec.europa.eu/scientific-committees/scientific-committee-health-environmental-and-emerging-risks-scheer_en

System Action: Human capacity building in multimodal data Integration and interdisciplinary models

Action involves various steps. In this first stage, the CoCreate project has initiated Reflection and we are in the process of developing clear goals and ensuring there is adequate preparation. The next stage is identifying appropriate methods to be included in the project. Because of the multi-dimensional focus, this may occur overtime as it becomes more apparent what will add to the knowledge base. Initially, this list has been identified as including neuroscientists, computer scientists etc. Identify which specific research will be undertaken and which models will be used. Identify which existing resources will be used and what new resources will have to be developed. Implement the plan and evaluate the results and communicate to other parties. I.e., Reflect, plan, act, observe. In this sub section that would involve building a model to facilitate interdisciplinary research and develop a guideline for such collaboration. Develop ML programmes which can incorporate data from a range of research methods e.g., imaging, legacy data.

Challenge overview:

- Multiscale disease signatures development, based on whole-brain computational modelling.
- How to integrate multimodal datasets.

- How can we ensure that advances in relevant basic science fields are integrated into the investigations of the etiology of clinical conditions?

Solution overview:

- Model building based on interdisciplinary research (from psychiatry to endocrinology, physiology, genetics, sociology, environmental, communication) to understand the causes, identify manifestations, markers.
- Scholarship Program for Multisupervisor / Interdisciplinary PhDs projects in EU.
- Example. Think beyond disease to the aging brain and the vulnerability of e.g., BBB, glymphatic system on the base of common variable/aim/target/condition.
- Build academic infrastructure: Interdisciplinary collaboration (data contribution, research trajectory), education, AI multimodal integration.
- Ensure the existence of appropriate scientific infrastructures that will allow rapid transmission of notable scientific findings (infrastructures must be highly interdisciplinary!).
- promoting continuing education and Actions within undergraduates and PhDs trajectories.

Collaborators needed: Engage with fellow EU lobby groups either through personal contacts or via the European Transparency Register -<https://ec.europa.eu/transparencyregister/public/homePage.do>

Characterisation of the action: Identify who should be engaged in the project. Provide a list of groups and persons and the type of funding that could be targeted. Engage with the groups and identify the willing collaborators. Communicate with interest groups and via various means to ensure people have the opportunity to contribute. Identify any funding groups at the national level.

Resources: Personnel: Key stakeholders who influence the type of research which is undertaken. Develop an interest group to communicate this to the broader community through for example, conferences, papers and other valued communication resources. Lobby groups responsible for funding to support a shift in focus so that funding is provided not only for research on cause of disease and the broader researcher agenda of a pre disease model of surveillance. Lobby pharmaceutical companies and lifestyle advocates to take a broader approach to preventative treatments.

System Action: Rethinking phenotypes based on Multimodal biomarkers

Challenge overview:

- Lack of clear phenotypes (Psychiatry).
- Lack of non-invasive biomarkers.
- Which lack of understandings stand in the way for the vision.
- Understanding the brain.
- Understanding pathways between body and brain.
- Heterogeneity and complexity of BD.
- The body brain pathway can be complicated by the time factor i.e., changes in the body will not be evident for some time later in the changes in the brain.

Solution overview:

- Develop new reliable tools to categorized (may not be a variable description based).
- Multimodal approach, advance in neuroimaging+ML for markers detection, extraction from overlapping characteristics specific one.
- Include non-neurological biomarkers which reflect changes in the brain.
- Move towards the idea of using the understanding we have about the brain to get a better knowledge regarding brain derived disorders.
- Data integration based on platforms and data we have access to develop new tools or solutions to generate new/modified phenotypes and health trajectories.

Collaborators needed: Specialized AI resources that could work together with data integration.

Characterisation of the action: Identify who should be engaged in the project in terms of key personnel and the types of groups that might benefit from the project or who are able to promote the project. Provide a list of groups and persons and the type of funding that could be targeted. Engage with the groups and identify the willing collaborators. Communicate with interest groups and via various means to ensure people have the opportunity to contribute.

Resources: Funding is one of the key resources that has to be found, however resources can range from EU centred groups and key international groups which are nation based or have a global reach such as the WHO and the UN.

Bringing the roadmap into life

The roadmap has been cocreated and designed with actionable points for actors to act upon to work towards achieving the overarching vision of improving the investigation of brain-related disorders. In addition, considerations on how to realise the vision of the roadmap was a significant part of the discussions. In the following, the participants' recommendations on how to bring the roadmap into life is addressed.

Establishing projects

The establishment of a mega-project to develop a new patient assessment seems unlikely to happen anytime soon. However, smaller steps can be taken through a strategic approach. One possible strategy involves establishing projects through a bottom-up process based on shared interest. This can be achieved by convening a steering committee and reaching out to other potential collaborators, starting informally at a society conference or other meeting.

Another important aspect is to connect with stakeholder organizations on an equal footing to learn about their respective needs and wishes. To achieve this, traditional stakeholder organizations, such as patient groups, need to be convinced about the benefits of this new way of doing science. It is important to describe how this approach can meet their needs and to work towards securing funding to support these initiatives.

In addition, lobbying politicians, such as ministers of science and education, to get involved in large projects like EBRAINS can also be an effective strategy. By highlighting the significance of these projects to the public, the public can become involved and press politicians to participate and support such initiatives.

It is crucial to communicate the significance of EBRAINS to society and to engage the EBRAINS community in project development. This can be done by informing stakeholders, patient groups, and politicians to allow opportunity and funding. Promoting the significance by using mass media and social networks can also be beneficial.

It is important to assess the current state, especially interest in society, and the significance of the future project to reach the attention of the society. It can be useful to get the first insight into public perception by speaking to health organizations and census to add some questions or drawing on their knowledge from previous questionnaires. Using stakeholder groups to access certain populations can help determine their training needs. For example, experts from SfN can be reached to determine their training needs, and patients can be reached through advocate groups akin to Alzheimer's Europe.

Unique issues and requirements of implementing personalized medicine, such as opt in/out of data usage and enough data point diversity to get "good matches," should be discussed with affected groups. Outreach to underrepresented groups via members of these communities can help to get the diversity and richness of data required to "parameter match" new patients to existing ones to determine clinical course of action. A pilot test can be done with one such group to gather data to answer a "small" research question. The aim is to learn and improve from such an initiative to improve the approach so that we can finally end up with the broad database we want.

Finally, focusing on synergies can be an effective strategy. For example, the FLAG-ERA Joint Transnational Call 2023 can be an opportunity to achieve synergy with the two large-scale European initiatives, Graphene Flagship and Human Brain Project - EBRAINS. The European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) 2021 Roadmap, the European Quantum Flagship, and the EU Health Policy Platform Annual Meeting: Stakeholders' Dialogue: Joint Statements, Study results, and discussion on 19 April are other potential opportunities to achieve synergy.

Continue the debate!

EBRAINS is an ambitious European initiative that aims to bring together neuroscience researchers and the latest technologies to advance our understanding of the brain and develop new treatments for brain disorders. However, for the project to achieve its full potential, it is essential to continue the debate on its vision and roadmap and to spread the word about the project's potential and current applications.

One way to continue the debate is to identify ambassadors for the CoCreate result who can help promote the project to a broader audience. These ambassadors could include scientists, policymakers, patient advocates, and media personalities with professional education in the field of neuroscience. By bringing together a diverse group of advocates, EBRAINS can raise awareness of its work and build a community around the project.

To reach a broader audience, it is also crucial to present the potential and current applications of the EBRAINS platform in layman's terms. By providing case studies that demonstrate how the technology can improve outcomes for people with brain disorders, such as blindness, epilepsy, cerebral palsy, and aging-related conditions, EBRAINS can help make its work more accessible to the general public. The project should aim to simplify its messaging and provide clear proof of concept that highlights the benefits of its work.

To aid in communicating the value of EBRAINS, the project could hire staff with skills in science communication and illustrators who can help create engaging visual content. This content could be shared on social media platforms and other communication channels to reach a broader audience.

National EBRAINS committees could also be formed to create collaborations with government and national stakeholders and build a sustainable infrastructure for EBRAINS. This infrastructure could include partnerships with research institutions, funding mechanisms, and policies that support the project's goals.

To sustain activity and communication between scientists, EBRAINS could improve the user-friendliness of its platform and provide training courses that show how to use the Jupiter notebook and compare data with the EBRAINS atlases. This training could help researchers better understand the capabilities of the platform and encourage collaboration between scientists.

EBRAINS could also engage with the EU Health Policy Platform and participate in its annual meeting to present its work and discuss its potential applications in the field of health. The project could set up a public outreach team to oversee the task of informing and engaging society through social and traditional media. This team could also develop a "magazine style" communication strategy to showcase near-future advancements in treatments and technology that demonstrate the potential benefits of the project.

Finally, EBRAINS could get in touch with "influencers" on platforms such as YouTube, TikTok, and Instagram, to reach a broader audience. By using simple language and focusing on real-world applications, EBRAINS can help build excitement and enthusiasm for its work and engage a new generation of supporters. Additionally, EBRAINS could participate in events such as the "night of sciences" and "Forskningens døgn" to engage with the public and showcase its work.

In conclusion, continuing the debate, presenting the potential and current applications of the EBRAINS platform, engaging with stakeholders and the public, and investing in science communication are crucial steps that EBRAINS can take to achieve its goals and advance our understanding of the brain.

Selling the vision

EBRAINS is an ambitious and revolutionary initiative that aims to bring together the brightest minds in research, technology, and medicine to leverage the latest advancements in Artificial Intelligence (AI) and improve treatments in clinical neurology, psychiatry, and potentially even metabolic disorders.

To convince funders, the vision needs to be clarified, simplified, and made more specific. Successful case stories should be presented, showcasing the benefits and impact of the EBRAINS platform. It is also important to get medical and clinical experts on board and to use a personalized approach in the headlines to attract the attention of potential funders.

It is essential to demonstrate that the investment made in EBRAINS has led to certain benefits already and that the project is on the road to achieving the next major outcome. The existing infrastructure is ready to be used and could provide further benefits.

Concrete markers of success should be included, with specific deliverables and impacts on society. EBRAINS is a unique infrastructure that is necessary to achieve the volume of data needed for precise models for data-driven personalized

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medicine. This will give the opportunity to be competitive with other scientific consortia and stay proactively engaged in the technology instead of simply following others.

When pitching to stakeholders, it is important to identify what they get out of it and allow them to input into the roadmap. Keywords such as "long-term reduced health costs" and "forefront of science, innovation, and technology" should be used when identifying science representatives in national governments.

Selling the vision to citizens should focus on personalized medicine, tailored treatment, prevention, and early detection. The benefits of EBRAINS should be emphasized, such as medicines that work, no mistreatments, and no misdiagnosis.

To summarize, EBRAINS is a game-changing initiative that has the potential to revolutionize the field of neuroscience and medicine. By showcasing successful case stories, demonstrating concrete markers of success, and using personalized approaches to pitch to stakeholders, the vision of EBRAINS can be effectively sold to funders and citizens alike.

How can HBP/EBRAINS help?

The Human Brain Project and EBRAINS have the potential to play a crucial role in supporting bottom-up initiatives in neuroscience research. Here are some recommendations and advice to HBP/EBRAINS on how they can help:

1. Bottom-up engagement of EBRAINS community for project development: One of the key advantages of EBRAINS is its expanding community of researchers, technologists, and clinicians from across Europe and beyond. EBRAINS can leverage this community to find partners within the platform for project development. EBRAINS can use its platform to facilitate project development, information support, promotion, recognition, and identification of EBRAINS and proposed projects. This could be done by inviting participants from co-create conferences to join a national committee and elaborate on the tools given to such a committee and the benefits for researchers that might consider taking on the task.
2. Providing/enabling PhD-student opportunities: EBRAINS can create specific PhD-student positions oriented towards the EBRAINS ecosystem. By doing this, EBRAINS can help to train the next generation of neuroscientists and neurotechnologists, who can contribute to the development of the platform and its tools. EBRAINS can develop and promote existing Instagram accounts, both for HBP and EBRAINS, to synchronize them with the webpage including community space. Neuroscience and neurotechnologies are hot topics that could help EBRAINS to be extremely popular/visible worldwide.
3. Help EBRAINS users find other users with shared goals: EBRAINS can provide a platform for researchers to find other users with shared goals and a place to self-organize/request resources. This could involve providing a list of positions/projects of interest defined by either EBRAINS or suggested by stakeholders. Funding for these projects will come from the organization that suggests the project/wants the work done. EBRAINS can also provide supervision and be the go-between for EBRAINS & stakeholders so that new recruits aren't involved with inter-organizational politics.
4. Lowering the barrier to communicating with stakeholder groups: EBRAINS can lower the barrier to communicating with stakeholder groups who want to work with researchers. This can be done by providing point of contact persons reachable via EBRAINS, instead of every researcher/university having to start from scratch and build contacts from square one. This could help to streamline the process of collaboration and reduce the time and effort required to establish new partnerships.

In conclusion, HBP/EBRAINS can play a crucial role in supporting bottom-up initiatives in neuroscience research. By leveraging its expanding community, providing opportunities for PhD-students, helping researchers find other users with shared goals, and lowering the barrier to communicating with stakeholder groups, EBRAINS can help to accelerate the development of innovative tools and solutions that can transform the field of neuroscience.

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EBRAINS Community

This CoCreation event on Improved Investigation of Brain-related Disorders is organized by the EBRAINS Community Building Team. EBRAINS Community is a growing online community within neuroscience, brain medicine, and brain-related technology. Whether you are looking for other EBRAINS users, would like to engage in research facilitated by the EBRAINS services and tools, or find elements of neuroscience and brain-related technology interesting, the odds are you will find like-minded in the EBRAINS Community.

Sign up for EBRAINS Community

Follow the link below and you will be sent directly to the first destination of your journey, the sign-up page. Simply sign-up with your EBRAINS Account or with your e-mail and click 'Sign up as Member'. The next step is then to verify your e-mail address through an e-mail that will be sent directly to your e-mail inbox. Give it a few minutes and remember to check your spam folder!

When you have signed up as a member and logged in, it is time for you to start building your personal profile. You simply follow the steps that you will be presented when you access your profile:

1. First name
2. Surname
3. Choose a minimum of one field of interest

Now press '**Publish to EBRAINS**' and start using the features and functions! You can always access your profile at a later time to fill in additional information or edit your profile.

Join the EBRAINS community here:

community.ebrains.eu

Human Brain Project

Behind EBRAINS CoCreate

EBRAINS CoCreate: Improved Investigation of Brain-related Disorders is run by The Danish Board of Technology, a part of the Human Brain Project and EBRAINS Community Building Team

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